

History of the Development of the Russian Language and its Significance on the World Scale

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Abstract. *This article discusses the history of the Russian language, the modern and ancient Russian (East Slavic) language, the views of linguists in its development, the role of the Russian language in the world and its teaching in schools and universities in many countries.*

Keywords: *language, Russian, East Slavic, Russian, Russians, Ukrainians, Belarusians, Kiev, Indo-European languages.*

Language is the key to all knowledge and nature. Language refers to social phenomena that exist in all periods of human society. The main purpose (or function) of language is to serve as a means of communication. Language is inextricably linked with thinking, human consciousness, and serves as a means of forming and expressing our thoughts and feelings. There are more than two thousand languages on our planet. Among them, the Russian language is one of the most common. It includes all linguistic tools used in communication between people. We all know that the Russian language is one of the largest languages in the world. The modern Russian language is a continuation of the Old Russian (Eastern Slavic) language. Slavic languages preserve Indo-European antiquity in grammar and vocabulary. (True, the most conservative of the living Indo-European languages are Baltic: Lithuanian and Latvian.)

This ancient heritage makes Russian (like other Slavic languages) very difficult, but pleasant. The Old Russian language was spoken by the East Slavic tribes who founded the Old Russian nation in the 9th century as part of the Kiev state. This language has great similarities with the languages of other Slavic peoples. But it already differs in some phonetic and lexical features. All Slavic languages (Polish, Czech, Slovak, Serbo-Croatian, Slovene, Macedonian, Bulgarian, Ukrainian, Belarusian, Russian) come from a common root - a single Proto-Slavic language, which probably existed until the 10th-11th centuries. Based on the single language of the ancient Russian people in the 14th and 15th centuries, as a result of the disintegration of the Kievan state, three independent languages appeared: Russian, Ukrainian and Belarusian became national languages. With the formation of nations and stages, the first Cyrillic writings appeared among the Eastern Slavs in the 10th century. In 988, books were written in Russian. The chronicle tells about many scientists who worked during the time of Yaroslav the Wise. Liturgical books are often suitable.

The original East Slavic manuscript books were mainly South Slavic manuscripts of the works of Cyril and Matthew, students of the creators of the Slavic script. In the process of writing letters, the original language was adapted to the East Slavic language. In addition, in our time, there is no single periodicity of the history of the literary language in Russian accepted by all linguists, but all researchers take into account the socio-historical and cultural-social conditions of development when constructing the periodization. . language _ Periodization of the history of the Russian literary language LP Yakubinsky, VV Vinogradov, GO Vinokura, BA Larina, DI Gorshkova, Yu.S. Sorokin and other linguists are based on observations that take into account the norms of the Russian literary language, its connection with ancient literary and linguistic traditions, common literary language and

dialects, social functions and areas of application of the Russian literary language.

Most philologists of the 18th and 20th centuries claimed that the basis of the Russian literary language was the Church Slavonic language that came to Russia with the adoption of Christianity. Some researchers have indirectly developed and are developing the theory of Church Slavonic foundations. Russian literary language (AI Sobolevsky, AA Shakhmatov, BM Lyapunov, LV Shcherba, NI Tolstoy, etc.). Thus, AI Sobolevsky wrote: "It is known that the Church Slavonic language was the first of the Slavic languages to be used literally", " After Cyril and Matthew , it first became a literary language among the Bulgarians, and then became a literary language. Serbs and Russians. "AA Shakhmatov noted as an example of the extraordinary complexity of the formation of the Russian literary language, the full reflection and completion of the assumption of the Church Slavonic basis of the Russian literary language, taken in the 18th century: "There is no other language in the world. possible "No" , he says.

The scientist firmly elevates the modern Russian literary language to the level of the Church Slavonic language: "The Russian literary language is the Russian language by its origin, which over the centuries has become closer to the living folk language and gradually has lost its form. Church Slavonic language. (of ancient Bulgarian origin)," was transferred to its soil. A. Shakhmatov, the ancient Bulgarian language not only became the written literary language of the Kiev state, but also had a great influence on the oral speech of the "educated strata of Kiev" as early as the 10th century, so the modern Russian literary language includes . many old Bulgarian book speech. It is believed that it contains many words and word forms.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In the process of analyzing this article, the methods of logicity, historicity, consistency and objectivity of scientific knowledge were widely used. The study analyzed the history of the development of the Russian language and its importance in the world. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's methodological guidelines for the study of history and spiritual heritage form the theoretical and methodological basis of the research.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS.

Since the middle of the 20th century, the study of the Russian language has spread throughout the world. Currently, the Russian language is taught in more than 100 countries of the world. In 1967, the International Association of Russian Language and Literature Teachers was established, and in 1973, the Russian Language Institute named after AS Pushkin was established. The Russian language is one of the most widespread and rich languages in the world, it is spoken by representatives of various nationalities outside the main distribution area, and they communicate not only with the native speakers of these languages, but also with yourself.

A complete description of the synonyms of the modern Russian literary language, their speech features and their use in the etiquette and culture of Russian speech was carried out by AP Evgenieva. As a result of hard work, he was released in 1975. one volume "Thesaurus. An information guide has been prepared" (editor's translation).

In 1997, a new explanatory dictionary of synonyms of the Russian language was created at the Russian Academy of Sciences named after VVVinogradov under the leadership of Yu.D.Apresyan. This dictionary is based on the principles of holistic description of the language. The dictionary describes semantic, pragmatic, communicative and other similarities and differences between synonyms, as well as the appearance of these differences in a partially neutral state. In general, in Russian linguistics, in addition to general dictionaries, graduate dictionaries for lower levels of education have also been developed. Russian linguists such as DN Ushakov, SE Kryuchkov, AN Tikhonov, PA Grushnikov, ZA Potikha, MR Lvov deal with these problems. In order to teach schoolchildren to work with a dictionary from a young age, various visual and interesting dictionaries have been created.

Professor MR Lvov, the creation of such educational dictionaries for students helps to increase the level of their independent work and provide them with quality and selected language materials. It should be noted that Professor MR Lvov is the author of various educational dictionaries for primary

school students. This includes "Dictionary of synonyms and antonyms of the Russian language", "Dictionary of antonyms of the Russian language for children of school age", "Distinguishing words and their meanings: polysemantic words, etc. Thematic groups, homonyms, synonyms, paronyms. ". , synonyms, antonyms, for example "Dictionary of antonyms of the Russian language", "Dictionary of antonyms of the Russian language".

These dictionaries are made up of words suitable for elementary school students. For example, "Dictionary of synonyms and antonyms of the Russian language" consists of five sections, in which young schoolchildren begin to work with synonyms and systematically move to antonyms, in which synonyms are antonymic relations, synonymy and polysemy of antonymic pairs there is. given systematically .

CONCLUSION

English and other languages used in foreign countries that are state or official languages, Russian is widely used outside of Russia. For example, it is used in various fields of international (interstate) communication. It acts as a "language of science" and serves as a means of communication between scientists of different countries, a means of codification and storage of universal knowledge. According to statistics, 60-70% of the world's information is published in English and Russian.

The Russian language is a necessary link in world communication systems (radio broadcasting, air and space communication, etc.). English, Russian, and other world languages are characterized not only by the specificity of state functions (for example, the function of a lingua franca, that is, an intermediary in the dissemination of knowledge and the equalization of its level in different countries); the function of the language of diplomacy, international trade, transport, tourism), but these languages were deliberately chosen for learning and using them.

That is, the subject of teaching in schools and universities of many countries, its legal recognition as a "working language" at the international level, the use of the Russian language by people, especially at the UN, international congresses and other places, testify to this. that its influence is significantly higher.

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